

REINFORCING COLLABORATIVE WRITING BY ORDER THINKING SKILLS WITH PERCEIVED VIABILITYⁱ

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Abstract:

This inquiry engrossed its participants in proactive tasks fundamentally covering strengthening collaborative writing through the order thinking skills channeled to five main components: varied designed tasks, collaboration process, order thinking skills integration, significance of the process to the writing output and Knowledge, Language and Organization (KLO) framework. The said approach is perceived as highly feasible in augmenting collaborative writing by 27 English language teachers as respondents possessing varied nationalities, length of teaching experiences, teaching levels and educational attainment. They further support that interweaving the five constituents are categorically essential to the approach's reinforcement as revealed by the computed *mode* fortified by the *median* and construed by a Likert Scale alongside *percentages* of weighed nominal data from responses. The results explicate that combining varied language tasks and facilitating collaborative procedures while integrating order skills under a KLO context tend to reinforce directive writing tasks in a collaborative viewpoint. It is suggested that a research relating to this method be administered to a greater population of students (learning factors) and teachers (design and instructions) to statistically measure effects, strengths and weaknesses to more profound perspectives for the establishment of a sturdy and promising blueprints for best practice in collaborative writing. This concept is inspired by the institution's B1 and B1+ level employing the Common European Frame of Reference (CEFR) curriculum for Languages through Cambridge University Press' textbooks on Reading and Writing (Unlock) where order thinking skills' significance is advocated.

Keywords: collaboration, collaborative writing, collaborative learning, order thinking skills, task designs, knowledge-language-organization, critical thinking

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1. Introduction

Collaborative writing (CW) as used in this study is expected to occur within learners' group involved with series of order thinking skills (OTS) integrated-activities in preparation to the performance of a common target output/s (Zaky, 2018; Brindley, Walti & Blaschke, 2009; Heidar, 2016; Haring-Smith, 1994) while they deal with well-planned tasks in conjunction to what Guerrero, Mejias, Collazos, Pino & Ochoa (2003) stress that designs of a well-specified learning setting could encourage collaborative tasks in larger groups alongside sequences of tasks embedding OTS for activation. It is believed that said concept may not materialize if they are not underpinned by diversified constructed tasks with variety of OTS; from lower order thinking skills (LOTS) to higher order thinking skills (HOTS). To facilitate favorable and probable existence of this principle, it is observed that collaboration necessitates tasks that integrate OTS under an abstracted framework called Knowledge- Language and Organization (KLO). As operationally stipulated in this structure, knowledge are the details or information about a subject derived from the type of materials that are chosen and completed for tasks which can generate the type of strategies teachers may employ (Block, 1991; Podromou, 2002). Learners get details from the materials as catalysts in dealing with connected activities. Language being the second element bears linguistic foci embedded in the tasks leading to the writing method. Organization as the third frameworks' component encompasses the rudiments that enable the whole writing output alongside related-activities. The significance of this framework's components such as knowledge is advocated by researchers who assert that OTS in teaching needs well-planned and regulated forms of initial scaffolding (Slavin, 1995; Kauchan & Eggen, 1998). In here, the activities that fall under knowledge may primarily serve as support consistent to (Talib & Cheung, 2017)'s findings which declared that scaffolding is operative in augmenting learning cognition such as CW. Evidently connected, Bodrova & Leong (1998) and Elicker (1995) affirm that scaffolding is functional when a groundwork of organized procedures are planned. Through sufficient amount of fortification provided, intended objectives will be directed. In this methodology where CW is a major factor alongside tasks and OTS, it is believed that arriving at a meaningful written product is highly attached to KLO.

This paper attempts to enlighten readers through probable answers to the following major questions that are intertwined in all the paper's components:

- 1) How viable is CW through OTS from teachers' perceptions based from the five (5) stated components?
 - a) designed tasks' relevance to writing output
 - b) collaboration process' application,
 - c) OTS application,
 - d) significance of the process to the writing output
 - e) relevance of the KLO framework to the entire process
- 2) What are the pedagogical implications of this approach?
- 3) How are the OTS integrated in the writing task designs?
- 4) How does OTS reinforce CW?
- 5) What are the significance of the KLO framework in a CW approach?

2. Literature Review

To visibly comprehend this strategy, one has to be acquainted with the relationships that exist among the five (5) relevantly interwoven-components while associating the rudiments of collaboration, collaborative learning (CL), CW, OTS, tasks designs and the KLO.

2.1 Collaboration

Extensive years of teaching the language define this writer's awareness that CL is the epilogue for outmoded learning setting and the prologue of contemporary instructive innovation engaging clustered beginners of diverse thinking levels towards a specific and functional purpose, tantamount to (Entezari & Taki, 2018) who claim that it is an eye-opener to unlock post- modernism away from old teaching styles; an instruction method where students work in groups to succeed in common academic goal (Vijayaratnam, 2012). CL is transformed as a creative procedure to enhance students' ability in acquiring intended outcomes. Moreover, authors such as Vygotsky (1978; Collins (2014), Bruner (1986), Lunsford (1991) and Davidson & Major (2014) reveal that the teacher is dominantly a facilitator rather than an active lecturer; a manager instead of a speaker for meaningful learning experiences by stimulating learners' OTS. Language educators should be aware that successful learning development should be student-centered. Additionally, Laam & Ghodsi (2011) impart that collaboration is a principle of interface making individuals accountable for their learning engagement as they impart acceptable potentials to their peers. Learners come together as a group for a specific objective to be achieved manifested by their outputs at the end. Hanjani (2015) recognizes collaboration as appropriate in enhancing their functional skills through group involvement by identifying and addressing each other's weaknesses to attain accuracy. Doing the tasks in groups where the real essence of CL demonstrated is backed by (Panitz, 1996) who claims that involvement tends to contribute students' social, cognitive and academic progress. As perceived in the presentation of this technique, CL likely produces interactive assistance within the group, gears to the assimilation of varied levels of understanding which they process for acceptance, promotes teacher facilitation centralizing learning progression to learners (Vygotsky, 1978; Collins, 2014; Bruner, 1986; Lunsford, 1991; Davidson & Major, 2014) where self-confidence may be built, reduces problems in project involvement, facilitates positive attitudes when dealing in common objectives, assists reasoning among members, stimulates mass participation and surfaces problem-solving skills that are naturally undertaken by them as sustained by (Fung, 2010) who acknowledges the vital structures of collaboration as real joint interface, concession, conflict organization and shared proficiency.

2.2 Collaborative learning

In proximity to the claims of many researchers, Pastor & David Perry (2010) regard CL as a teaching tactic which increases growth, experience and social communication in an academic environment while discouraging nonparticipation, replication and individuality. In CL, students can renovate their own learning strategies and select their own objectives simultaneously responsible for what they learn and how they gain knowledge of a topic.

Davidson & Major, (2014) share that one goal of CL is situating participants to be accountable for their functions in doing group work. It is for this reason that CL necessitates a transformation of obligation free from the control of language coaches. By this measure, students as a group can learn by their own. Both authors further unveils that CL facilitates students in the construction of knowledge as one. In this type of learning, formulation of knowledge is a result of their group interchange (Zaky, 2018; Storch, 2013; Guerrero, Mejías, Collazos, Pino & Ochoa, 2014; Al Makhzoomi & Awad, 2010)'s investigations withstand that CL assists students to acquire knowledge and skills that are more heightened than independent learning. CL through its activities includes creative thinking for the advancement of OTS (Klimovienė, Urbonienė & Barzdžiukienė, 2006).

2.4 Collaborative writing

In addition, collaboration is where collaborative language learning has been derived generating collaborative writing (CW) and cooperative writing despite each one's differences that exist. Conferring to (Ede & Lunsford, 1990; Zhang, 2018), CW is a coordinated joint effort throughout the writing process transforming writers to impart responsibilities for the entire output's accomplishment while a cooperative writing comprises conveyed and assigned responsibilities narrowed down to a specific part such as a small group where members are divided into pairs. For instance, in an essay, one writes the introduction and others are apportioned to perform remaining parts. Furthermore, Elola (2010) articulates that CW tasks enable members to comprehend the examination of the groups' thoughts to cultivate an overall quality of their composition aside from the content. Skills are put together by learning through corrections of grammar errors, critiquing ideas which can lead also in a thorough production of their work's outline sustained by numerous ideas that are weighed and considered for implementation. As an emphasis, Rao (2007) points out that instead of focusing on teaching students how to produce correct writing products; English educators should adopt a process-based scheme for learners to provide them opportunities to interact with each other. Additionally, according to (Webb, 1982) HOTS are advanced by CL which this article attempts to manifest. To this author, learners will devotedly be engrossed in the instructive procedure. They collaboratively work together to demonstrate an efficient level of interface. Students are placed in a situation of varied thinking responsibilities. Indispensably pertinent, Vygotsky, (1978) argues that by language acquisition, thinking elevates reasoning as it backs outdated tasks like reading and writing. In here, Vygotsky encourages language trainers to offer prospects among them to perform conversation about their learning which create crucial interchanges among them promoting deeper understanding. Involvement of motivation is encouraged for CL. Investigating CW's positive effects to learners; Suwantarathip & Wichadee (2014) reported that participants had high positive attitudes toward CW activities alluding to this writer's descriptive study that attempts to reveal the potentials of it in directing learners in accomplishing their written works. Likewise, there are multiple implications on the promising effects of CW for instance: they are empowered because the knowledge formulated originated from them (Kellogg, 2008), they are willing to take the chance with their writing styles being critiqued, they give importance to planning procedures and expository attempts (Phillips, 1992), they have all the chance to evaluate

group created syntactical structures, they combined the high level of their knowledge instead of minding their waterloo (Orunsolu, Vincent, Adebayo & Bamgboye, 2010), learners are given instantaneous readers and reactions that are detrimental in identifying the necessities of their projects for comprehensive construction and they meticulously decide what terminologies to use (Caviedes, Meza & Rodrigues, 2016) while creating some changes meaningful to their work sufficiently. Additionally, current educators in CW observed some favorable effects of it to learners. They interact to ignite cognitive processes and outside tasks are being converted into cognitive learning through estimate and assumption (Shehadeh, 2011). Their waterloos and incapacities are identified by each member; their strengths are assembled into solid foundation (Aminloo, 2013) which they can manipulate as catalysts in the writing project's accomplishments. Collaboration provides learner opportunities to read appraise and address everyone's writing (Suwantarathip & Wichadee, 2014). Writers shape meaningful and well-directed expositions apart from others who compose in isolation (Jalili & Shahrokhi, 2017). In this method, it is professed that they demonstrate different levels of capacities to accomplish writing which naturally occurs in native and second language learning (Talib, & Cheung, 2017). To (Bakhshayesha, 2016; Sadler & Kusumawati, 2017) they in a collaborative setup produce superior amount of higher levels of terminologies due to shared vocabulary than individually-assisted writing. Moreover, Huett & Koch (2011) exposes the value of time in accomplishing assigned job which possibly will add in refining procedures. Similarly, CW necessitates distribution of roles such as acting as drafter, reviewer or an editor. Comparatively, Shehadeh (2011) argues that it augments everyone recognizing the interactive characteristics of CW method. Some articulate that CW is a concession procedure that indorses dynamic thinking (Latawiec, Anderson, Ma & Nguyen 2016). In parallel, Shehadeh (2011) reveals that it is an educational tool to inspire learner collaboration and create a constructive communal ambiance in the classroom which means writing doesn't need to be an isolated learning act. Studies have discovered that CW tends to confirm recommendable quality of work (Yeh, 2014). For (Aminloo, 2013), CW results could be superior in contrast to individual writing since thoughts that are functional are accepted while the recessive ones are filtered. As a valuable consequence, CW discloses members' weaknesses and potentials that are being weighed and considered for the production of improved written projects.

2.5 Order thinking skills in collaborative writing

The Order thinking skills (OTS) is central in administering CL such as CW. (Brewster, 1999) explains that (Bloom, 1956) pioneered the famous hierarchy of six OTS sequenced from LOTS to HOTS originally known as knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation which to these days, (Anderson, et al 2001) transformed into remembering, understanding, applying, analyzing, evaluating and creating. Bloom's principle is a substantial launching point among other scholars for the enhancement of learning practices. Tantamount to (Collins, 2014) who asserts that Bloom's Taxonomy is not the sole basis of OTS's teachings, nonetheless is generally operated. She proclaims that the principle embedded in (Bloom, 1956)'s work are the main major sources of transformative teaching of OTS. Collins additionally points out that the cognitive domain is where OTS are generated

alongside affective and psychomotor domains. It is substantial to note that the cognitive domain produces the OTS by which even in learning foreign languages, they play major roles in the cognitive advancement of students (Chapple & Curtis, 2000; Davidson, 1995). They uphold the existence of empirical evidence that OTS sustain the efficiency of language acquisition. Factually connected, Brookhart (2010) stresses that thinking as a way of learning is transferred in real-life. Knowledge is not just acquired. This knowledge is applied in their real life-environment. Barahal (2008) sees the involvement of OTS in learning as a process of manipulating sequence of inner thoughts that are intellectual, inquisitive, explorative, perceptive and descriptive, associative and involving which Zaky (2018) confirms. In like manner, Vijayaratnam (2012) previously affirms that their OTS and group consciousness can be advanced through figuring out solutions to a given problem connected to (Gokhale, 1995) who earlier proclaims that if the purpose of teaching is to develop critical thinking (CT) and problem-solving skills, then CL is more beneficial. Said principle is currently strengthened by (Talib & Chung, 2017) who together claim that CW is effective in improving accuracy of students' writing and CT. Singh, Singh, Tunku, Mostafa & Singh (2018) infer that one among the efficient ways to impart HOTS to learners is when CT and creative thinking are incorporated in carefully planned activities. Klimovienė, Urbonienė & Barzdžiukienė (2006) asserted that creative thinking manifests CT in worth involving-tasks.

2.6 Order thinking skills, tasks designs & collaborative writing overtones

Setting the right objectives may depend on teachers' creative styles. Having appropriate objectives is dependent on the kind of tasks and materials instructors may choose, to design and utilize while integrating OTS. Brookhart (2010) argues that if they think of HOTS as a way of problem solving, language educators should prepare appropriate aims in instructing students on how to distinguish them by constructing new concepts to address it. These solutions may be in classrooms or in natural contexts. Zaky (2018), Grief (2007) and Lidawan & Chua (2018) suppose that active CW projects need the existence of group awareness through which participation and coordination might be created by the teacher for tangible instructional styles. As to the value of tasks in CT, Singh, Choy & Lee (2015) state that CL tend to aid students on reflecting the content and situations of the tasks that they have to carry out. This form of learning is seen to increase their confidence and motivation to communicate with their peers in a second language with higher degree of tasks completion. In connection to learning, possible achievement of this should engross them to tasks that are created primarily functional in their natural world. This principle brings us closer to (Shirkhani & Fahim, 2011) who collectively affirm that mentors should include activities that motivate learners to think about the main aims of the lesson with evolving CT skills. They further express that the type of activities use in assessing language learners determines the objectives of learning where simple exercises that may start from memorizing to substituting, among others promote CT skills though reasoning, collaborating and enquiring questions among themselves. Furthermore, Shirkhani & Fahim (2011) argue that teachers should co-create criteria for appraisal to foresee the association of these standards to the goals of the tasks. This concept exposes a universal truth that no teacher has the monopoly of knowledge mastery and that there are some points that one may have overlooked but may possibly be

observed by fellow teachers for augmentation if not to be made outright. Supplementary to task design for OTS,

Vdovina & Gaibisso (2013) express that cautiously writing a lesson plan could aid to organize the targeted learning objectives. Some parts of the lesson plan may include additional elements that serve as triggering factors that assimilate CT such as prerequisites, instructional objectives, reinforcement activities, and assessment. Implementing this suggestion tend to empower the teacher to synchronize these task elements in instruction. Equally central, Wilks, (2005) imparts that designed curriculum should comprise tasks that combine OTS. It should concentrate on instructing students skills not in isolation but in contexts or situations. These lessons should be learned for the purpose of natural functions such as solving, self-monitoring, reading and study strategies and CT as consequences of inspired learning advocated by (Vygotsky, 1962) whose previous affirmation to these days highlights that knowledge construction occurs within social backgrounds involving student-student and expert-student collaboration in dealing with real world problems or tasks that build on everyone's language, skills and familiarity shaped by their respective culture. Equally connected, Jaganathan & Subramaniam (2016) revealed that when giving task-based assignments, the teacher should emphasize the OTS' potentials in the performance of the project to be completed even within a short and specific duration of time as observation and facilitation for the students' incorporation of HOTSs exists. Remarkably relevant to others' prerogatives, Brookhart (2010) emphasizes that constructing an assessment for HOTS always involves three basic principles where two closely relate to tasks designing: specifying visibly and precisely what to be evaluated and designing the tasks or evaluating items that necessitate learners to exhibit the targeted knowledge or skill. This interrelates to (Correia, 2006) that activities assumed as dynamic may include creating diagrams and filling in tables. These tasks may facilitate them to interchange with the text and among matters to be learned in triggering group collaboration involving the teacher as a facilitator. Kauchak & Eggins (1998) propose the following guidelines in involving students in OTS-based tasks which are reflected in this paper's presentation of tasks: employment of scaffolding, provision of outlined demonstrations, deliberations of CT activities and facility of chances for learners to exercise solving- problems. In conjunction to what they have assumed, Brewster (1999) articulates activities that may reflect OTS can be those that may evaluate result, ease practical inquiries, define and record observations, discover arrangements, recognize likenesses and variances; compare outcomes and provide inferences among other forms. Consequently, in formulating writing tasks for language learning, Handley & Miner (1998) reveal that writing processes should task learners to recognize writing as a conglomeration of CT activities. This perception could be comparably applied to teachers in regarding writing task designs as cognitive activities that may require brainstorming, revising and finalizing before they are served to learners.

Griefs (2007) advises that making collaboration project successful will depend on how teachers select the materials, cautiously prepare CW activities without neglecting the pre-writing tasks. In advocacy to this principle, Lidawan & Chua (2018) and Bikowski & Vithanage (2016) consent that CW activates teachers to be imaginative in performing their approach. This could be realized by the materials chosen and how tasks are sensibly

formulated. They infer that tasks should be appropriately presented alongside suitable strategy on how these are to be demonstrated. In the same pattern of thoughts aligned to task designs in CW, Thomas & Thorne (2009) suggest that instructions that are planned to teach HOTS should be equipped with appropriate concepts, schema and visualization. In visualization, thinking is not always generated in written forms which allow students to conclude. They assert that inferences such as deriving conclusions from given evidences should be present. This is to say that designed instructions equipped with concepts, schema and visualization gear to the learners' manipulation of OTS as they approach the intended outcomes such as the CW output that is being introduced in this paper. Teachers need techniques to succeed in teaching by planning and self-cultivation (Yen & Halili, 2015) activates the teaching of the OTS. They may include how materials are designed in order to create one's strategy. To them, when professional development engagements are regularly exercised by teachers, instruction may be effortlessly demonstrated as consequences of acquired understanding that suitably direct student' functionally advanced HOTS. Visockienė (2001) elaborates that one of the causes of modification in education is the expansion of learners' CT that chiefly influences the contexts of modern educational transformation; thus, Shanker (1985), Brown (1994), Lambright (1995) and Allamnakhrah (2012) campaign that setting educators to teach thinking skills creates students' high level of expertise. CT is an indispensable component of the academe since this is a primary measure that learning is mixed to a discipline (Klimovienė, Urbonienė & Barzdžiukienė, 2006). As Kurfiss (2001) declares, if they are regularly practiced, higher forms of their OTS will turn operational by contents that are well-designed and expounded in real-life contexts.

Additionally, Zaky (2018) acknowledged that CL in classrooms should have more inputs for learners to use in decision making, to get them involve on different standpoints and to deal with diversified writing capabilities. Correspondingly relevant, Kauchak & Eggins (1998) point out some relevant ideas that can be associated with task designs and how they may be successfully attained in directions for OTS: align learning goals, objectives, content ideas and skills, learning tasks, assessment activities and teaching aids or materials; establish organized activities and procedures and illuminate the task clearly. When it comes to inspiring learners for serious involvement, students likewise may perhaps be interested when motivation is inculcated in course designs as brace system to what they are going to complete (Brindley, Walti & Blaschke, 2009). Above all, curriculum improvement may possibly add to the galvanization of courses that can create OTS prolifically when appropriately underpinned by regimented activities. But if they are just intended to highlight awareness, only initial fractions of CT are stimulated. To explain this notion, Benko (2013) conveys that tasks scaffold the writing instructions even before, during and after the writing process. She mentions some guidelines that introduce the tasks attempted in this paper. The writing task should be suitably stimulating for learners and the constructed tasks should allow the learners in acquiring other skills and schemes that are feasible to both the writing activities and the presented tasks. For this matter, they should employ graphic organizers to enable them to follow provided details that are supportive to the writing organization.

2.7 The KLO Concept in the approach

The KLO aids the whole process in forms of questions through serving as guides in administering the reinforcement of CW. It comprises knowledge (K), language (L) and organization (O) that oversee the whole learning process in forms of questions as displayed on *Table 17*. Benko (2013) proposes that scaffolding for prewriting, during and at the end of post writing processes have to be delivered in different features and constructions. In this paper, KLO rudiments and the tasks showcase variations of activities as diverse ways of scaffolding the process.

a. Knowledge includes provision of materials for information gathering among learner, processing the information gathering through varied activities, generating exchanges among the participants to share standpoints, serving the information processing, generating OTS' initial operation and relating activities to the writing project. Lidawan & Chua (2018), Lidawan & Gabayno (2018) and Marzano (2004) maintain that background knowledge about the content is one of the sturdiest signs how well the learners are going to acquire innovative information associated to the content. It sustains the idea that provision of background knowledge out of the materials with their conforming tasks produces their capabilities to advance towards the stages in accomplishing intended outcomes. The background knowledge is distinguished as a way of scaffolding for intended direction as additionally reinforced by (Zaky, 2018) as he explores that in CL, members employ contextual knowledge integrating prior experience and skill growth along with the determined means that may well address their learning necessities. Analogous to that thought, Singh, Singh, Tunku, Mostafa, & Singh (2018) impart that the strategies which the educators use will assist the learners to stimulate their CT. Therefore, they will not just acquire awareness, but are made to manipulate gathered knowledge and create some functional standards out of them. Said importance has been emphasized by Bereiter & Scardamalia (1987) advocate that their knowledge provides methods of changing ideas, aids in adapting concepts and leads to the construction of orderly information that can promote comprehensibility, acceptability and usefulness of the passage being used for learning.

b. Language as the framework's component comprises provision of language forms to be mainly operated, teacher stimulation of their inferences through the language, performance of the language activities that are remarkable in writing, incorporation of OTS while they perform the activities and the connection of activities as whole for CW project's accomplishment (Lidawan & Chua, 2018; Lidawan & Gabayno, 2018). Likewise, collaborative scaffolding of language and content through tasks is crucial within the lessons. The interface between the learners and teachers generate real learning as Kuiper, Smit, De Wachter & Elen (2017) put it. As previously recognized by (Chin, 2000), operative writing preparation delivers abundantly formulated prospects for their abstract and language advancement. (McCarrier, Pinnell & Fountas, 2000; Faraj, 2015) advocate the reason why series of activities incorporate language learning opportunities as the learners move into the writing stage (organization) which is prescribed in this framework.

c. Organization being the third component of the propositioned structure involves the activities for writing, collaboration alongside language and OTS which are to be withstood by the presence of varied activities for CW, provision of ample time for learners to arrive at

functionally unified thoughts and sequenced parts prior to writing, existence of series of activities as prerequisites in gathering details enough for the students to carry-out the writing process, embedding components of organizing knowledge prior to writing, presence of OTS in the series of activities and the connection of these in the writing process evidently sustained by (Zaky, 2018; Lidawan & Chua, 2018; Lidawan & Gabayno, 2018; Kauchak & Eggen, 1998; Brindley, Walti & Blaschke, 2009; Thomas & Thorne, 2009; Yen & Halili, 2015; Faraj, 2015). *Table 1* features reinforced CL principles that are common among researchers applicable to reinforcing writing pertinent to this system.

2.8 CL principles common among researchers

Common claims	Advocacies
group commonly impart and incorporate multiple standpoints	Vygotsky, 1978; Collins, 2014; Lunsford, 1991; Davidson & Major, 2014; Vijayaratnam, 2012; Fung, 2010; Pastor & David Perry, 2010
emphasis is on learners roles; teacher facilitates	Davidson & Major, 2014; Vijayaratnam, 2012; Pastor & David Perry, 2010
learners generate variety of ideas to manifest levels of thinking	Klimovienė, Urbonienė, & Barzdžiukienė, 2006; Vijayaratnam, 2012; Gokhale, 1995; Vygotsky, 1978; Collins, 2014; Panitz, 1996; Lunsford, 1991; Pastor & David Perry, 2010
team's accountability to each everyone's roles	Collins, 2014; Vijayaratnam, 2012; Lunsford, 1991; Davidson, & Major, 2014; Fung, 2010; Webb, 1985; Fung, 2010; Pastor and David Perry, 2010; Singh, Singh, Tunku, Mostafa & Singh, 2018; Klimovienė, Urbonienė & Barzdžiukienė, 2006
distributed roles that connects with each other's roles; prioritizing assigned works	Lunsford, 1991; Davidson & Major, 2014; Vijayaratnam, 2012; Pastor & David Perry, 2010; Fung, 2010; Singh, Sedhu, Choy & Lee 2015
constructive teamwork	Lunsford, 1991; Davidson, & Major, 2014; Singh, Sedhu, Choy & Lee 2015
sociocognition is taught and reinforced by goals	Vygotsky, 1978; Collins, 2014; Davidson & Major, 2014; Fung, 2010; Singh, Singh, Tunku, Mostafa & Singh, 2018; Klimovienė, Urbonienė & Barzdžiukienė, 2006
learning emanates from the students	Davidson & Major, 2014; Vijayaratnam, 2012; Pastor & David Perry, 2010
The teacher interacts and facilitates.	Davidson & Major, 2014; Vijayaratnam, 2012; Bikowski, & Vithanage, 2016
upholds interaction	Webb, 1985; Davidson, & Major, 2014; Fung, 2010; Pastor & David Perry, 2010; Laal & Ghodsi, 2011
shared team management	Webb, 1985; Collins, 2009; Lunsford, 1991; Fung, 2010; Pastor & David Perry, 2010
group processing/solving issues	Vygotsky, 1978; Collins, 2014; Lunsford, 1991; Davidson & Major, 2014; Fung, 2010; Pastor & David Perry, 2010
interpersonal communication development not intrapersonal	Vygotsky, 1978; Collins, 2014; Lunsford, 1991; Davidson & Major, 2014; Pastor & David Perry, 2010
alleviate learner segregation	Vygotsky, 1978; Lunsford, 1991; Davidson, & Major, 2014; Fung, 2010; Pastor & David Perry, 2010
subject specific discussions/engagement with peers	Webb, 1985; Lunsford, 1991; Davidson & Major, 2014; Singh, Sedhu, Choy & Lee, 2015
allow cross cultural consciousness	Webb, 1985; Vygotsky, 1978; Davidson & Major, 2014; Singh, Sedhu, Choy & Lee, 2015; Fung 2010

self-confidence/individual value recognition	Davidson & Major, 2014; Pastor & David Perry, 2010; Singh, Sedhu, Choy & Lee 2015
mutual goals	Collins, 2014; Davidson & Major, 2014; Pastor & David Perry, 2010; Fung, 2010; Singh, Singh, Tunku, Mostafa & Singh, 2018; Klimovienė, Urbonienė & Barzdžiukienė, 2006
real life social and employment situation preparation	Vygotsky, 1978; Collins, 2014; Davidson & Major, 2014; Pastor & David Perry, 2010
weighing and considering points of each members	Singh, Sedhu, Choy & Lee 2015; Singh, Singh, Tunku, Mostafa & Singh, 2018; Klimovienė, Urbonienė & Barzdžiukienė, 2006; Yeh, 2014; Aminloo, 2013; Phillips, 1992; Orunsolu, Vincent, Adebayo & Bamgboye, 2010; Caviedes, Meza & Rodrigues, 2016; Talib, & Cheung, 2017

Table 1: Collaborative learning principles common in collaborative writing investigations

3. Methodology

3.1 The instrument

To obtain the level of viability of this technique presented among 27 participants who were grouped and had an actual manipulation of the specified activities, an evaluation was provided to them to assess the method which had been applied through their workshop immersion. The writer enabled the workshop's evaluation tool as a data instrument. The evaluation paper instructed them to rate the approach to show the extent of their perceptions using a Likert Scale from 1 to 5 in terms of the specified individual items found in *Table 3*. Additional instrument that had been used is the Likert Scale of five categories that contains numerical and descriptive rating had further completed the results from the data.

Framework of the OTS by (Anderson, Krathwohl, Airasian, Cruikshank, Mayer, Pintrich, Wittrock et al., 2001) found in *Table 2* is used as the basis of ascending OTS which determine the subskills of the activities classified as LOTS and HOTS.

Lower order thinking skills			Higher order thinking skills		
Remembering Memory is used to produce or retrieve definitions, facts, or lists, or to recite previously learned information.	Understanding constructing meaning from different types of functions	Applying carrying out/ or using/implementing procedures in a given situation	Analyzing breaking materials or concepts into parts, determining how the parts relate	Evaluating making judgments based on criteria and standards	Remembering Memory is used to produce or retrieve definitions, facts, or lists, or to recite previously learned information.

Table 2: Order skills framework

(Adapted from Anderson, Krathwohl et al., 2001, with a few changes)

3.2 Respondents

27 English teachers participated in the workshop with diverse length of teaching experience; levels taught and language education.

3.3 Statistics

This involved descriptive analysis entailing basic statistics through the engagement of mode in measuring central tendency of responses. Since mode could give limited information of the distribution for the data's central tendency or might be misleading, the writers thought of reassuring results through the median. It is a fact that when data is normally distributed, the median is the same score as the mode. As components are being described through mode, median is interspersed in the discussion of results. Equally vital, percentages (%) were additionally manipulated in gaging subjects' extent of responses as the interpretations unfold. This teaching model comprises varied tasks that were designed through a silent film. In the designed tasks, the LOTS and HOTS were assimilated for the purpose of scaffolding the writing output. The tasks were passed through to a pool of teachers specializing in language teaching for initial assessment prior to presentation.

The concept is administered to the participants in a simulated class. Tasks are carried-out till varied outputs of writing are made by every group with similar guidelines. The OTS embedded in the tasks are analyzed through the subskills that occurred in every activity that are reflected in *Table 13* herein. The teaching principle is evaluated by teachers using the rudiments of *Table 3* which is a questionnaire that attempts to strengthen the significance of the components in the approach covering the said tasks, process of its administration towards the output, incorporation of OTS, implication of collaboration in the process and the relationship of the KLO to the whole process.

A. Designed tasks' relevance to writing output
Descriptive Scale & Number Scale
Very High (5) High (4) Moderate (3) Low (2) Very Low (1)
B. Collaboration process' application
Descriptive Scale & Number Scale
Very High (5) High (4) Moderate (3) Low (2) Very Low (1)
C. Order thinking skills application for reinforcement
Descriptive Scale & Number Scale
Very High (5) High (4) Moderate (3) Low (2) Very Low (1)
D. significance of the process to the writing output
Descriptive Scale & Number Scale
Very High (5) High (4) Moderate (3) Low (2) Very Low (1)
E. Relevance of the KLO framework to the process
Descriptive Scale & Number Scale
Very High (5) High (4) Moderate (3) Low (2) Very Low (1)

Table 3: Participants' Evaluation Tool

From this questionnaire, components used in the analyses are specifically identified. These are contained in *Table 4* allocated as component A, B, C, D & E.

Component A	Component B	Component C	Component D	Component E
Tasks' relevance to the target output	Collaboration process application	Order thinking skills' application for reinforcement	Significance of the process to the writing output	Relevance of the KLO framework to the process

Table 4: Approach's components

4. Results & Interpretation

The data collected (*Table 5 and 6*) are analyzed initially using mode and corroborated by the median (*Table 7a*) to measure the central tendency for descriptive analysis through the use of a 5 range Likert Scale. The use of percentages (*Table 7b*) reinforced the analysis.

A. Mode

Summary					
Components	A	B	C	D	E
Mode	4	4	4	4	4
Range	4	4	4	4	4
Point value	3.41-4.20	3.41-4.20	3.41-4.20	3.41-4.20	3.41-4.20
Descriptive rating	high	high	high	high	high

Table 5: Mode analyzed per component among all respondents

Summary		
Mode	4	
Point value	4	
Range	3.41-4.20	
Descriptive rating	high	
Percentage	19 /27 =70 .307% high	6 /27= 22.2 % very high 2/27= 7.40 moderate

Table 6: Mode per component from individual respondents

Group responses' modes are computed per item: the common recurring number is 4 among the five components (*Table 5*). Individual responses per component are obtained and it generated the same result to that of the group's responses. The computed mode is 4 (*Table 6*). Both groups responses and individual responses' outcomes displayed respondents' perception as of high viability as interpreted by the Liker Scale (*Table 8*).

B. Median

Component A	Component B	Component C	Component D	Component E
4	4	4	4	4
4	4	4	4	4
Median	4	4	4	4
Range	3.41-4.20	3.41-4.20	3.41-4.20	3.41-4.20
Point Value	4	4	4	4
Descriptive value	High	High	High	High

Table 7a: Median obtained from responses per component among all respondents

To further fortify the reliability of the specific mode as a measure of central tendency, median is employed. It generated 4 as a median which falls under the point value of 4 in the Likert Scale (*Table 8*). Number 4 has a range of 3.41- 4.2 thus, its descriptive rating is measured with high viability.

C. Percentages

Components' percentage are computed by dividing the frequency into the number of respondents (27) then multiplying it by one hundred(100), tantamount to the equation, $X/27 \times 100 = \%$.

Components	$\% = f/27.100$	$\% = f/27.100$	$\% = f/27.100$	$\% = f/27.100$
A	2(0)	3 (0)	4 (14)	5 (13)
Percentage	0%	0%	51.85%	55.5%
B	2(0)	3(2)	4 (16)	5 (9)
Percentage	0%	7.40%	59.25%	33.33%
C	2(1)	3(4)	4 (16)	5 (6)
Percentage	3.70%	14.81%	59.25%	22.22%
D	2(0)	3 (1)	4 (16)	5(10)
Percentage	0%	11.11%	59.25%	37.03%
E	2(0)	3(4)	4 (17)	5(6)
Percentage	0%	14.81%	62.96%	22.22%

Table 7b: Percentages of responses

As stipulated in the *Table 7b*, the highest percentages of the components from A to E are confined under the highlighted fourth column which means that majority of the respondents noticed the components to be highly viable to the approach when we refer to the Likert Scale (*Table 8*).

Point Values	Range	Descriptive Rating
5	4.21-5	Very High viability
4	3.41-4.20	High viability
3	2.61-3.40	Moderate viability
2	1.81-2.60	Low viability
1	1.00 – 1.80	Very Low viability

Table 8: The Likert Scale to determine perceived relevance

Results are interpreted through components to explicate the general results of the approach's viability as it has been earlier stipulated aside from the introduced approach as entrenched in the whole research. It has been discovered that the overall statistical computations of the components' viability is of highly applicable as a teaching approach determined by the mode, median and percentages from the participants' perceptions.

Component A: Designed tasks' relevance to writing output

Mode shows that 4 is dominantly recurring corresponding to the scale which is descriptively interpreted as high. This Further enlightens that the varied designed tasks have high potential to scaffold the intended CW output (Slavin, 1995; Kauchan & Eggen, 1998; Talib & Cheung, 2017; Bodrova & Leong, 1998; Elicker, 1995; Benko, 2013). It also expounds that knowledge and language are contained in varied tasks for the purpose of the target output.

The median supports the mode. Both indicate that the designed tasks' relevance to the intended writing output according to the participants' perceptions is high. This promotes

that without the carefully planned tasks, (Brindley, Walti & Blaschke, 2009; Benko, 2013; Zaky, 2018; Kauchak & Eggen, 1998; Thomas & Thorne, 2009; Yen & Halili, 2015; Faraj, 2015; Slavin, 1995; Talib & Cheung, 2017; Bodrova & Leong, 1998; Elicker, 1995) the writing output couldn't be accomplished.

Being high in its significance as a component to the approach, 51 % of the respondents has considered this component's viability. *Table 9* statistically displays the details that sustain component A's judgement.

Median (Mdn)	4
Mode	4
Point value	4
Range	3.41-4.20
Descriptive Rating	High
Percentage	51%
No of respondents out of 27	14

Table 9: Component A: Designed tasks' relevance to writing output

Component B: Collaboration process' application

Collaboration process' mode shows that 4 is recurring corresponding to its descriptive scale which is high. This result manifests that the interactive process is feasible in reinforcing the process of writing. This could be attributed for the reason that communication occurred in the performance of the activities among its members (Entezari & Taki, 2018; Vijayaratnam, 2012; Ede & Lunsford, 1990; Zhang, 2018; Elola, 2010; Webb, 1982; Kellogg, 2008; Orunsolu, Vincent, Adebayo & Bamgboye, 2010; Caviedes, Meza & Rodrigues, 2016; Talib & Cheung, 2017; Bakhshayasha, 2016; Aminloo, 2013).

Congruent to the mode (4), the median (4) supports that the collaboration process' application is high as shown in the details of *Table 10*. It indicates that the procedures are pertinent to the aimed writing output. This refers to the fact that successful CW activities tend to be guided by well-planned procedures (Kauchak & Eggen, 1998; Shirkhani & Fahim, 2011; Shehadeh, 2011; Latawiec, Anderson, Ma & Nguyen, 2016; Huett & Koch, 2011). In this case, the writing steps demonstrate a collaboration process that can be applied in CW.

51% of the respondents understood that the collaboration process application of this approach is high. *Table 10 & Table 7b* demonstrate its statistical features.

Median (Mdn)	4
Mode	4
Point value	4
Range	3.41-4.20
Descriptive Rating	high
Percentage	59.25
No of respondents	16/27

Table 10: Component B: Collaboration process' application

Component C: Order thinking skills application for reinforcement

Mode shows that the series of numbers 4 are dominantly recurring. As described in the Likert Scale as high, the participants have noticed a pattern of OTS which is dependent on the tasks given to them. Analyses of the tasks demonstrated that the OTS existed in the tasks and that as the participants dealt with these activities, the OTS have been ascending (Brindley, Walti & Blaschke, 2009; Benko, 2013; Zaky, 2018; Kauchak & Eggen, 1998; Thomas & Thorne, 2009; Yen & Halili, 2015; Faraj, 2015; Slavin, 1995; Talib & Cheung, 2017; Bodrova & Leong, 1998; Elicker, 1995). As they climbed into higher levels, the target output is given enough foundation to be constructed. It is inferred that the principle of this technique could be realized through the spread of OTS in the tasks administered to the participants. Tasks manipulated OTS framework (*Table 12*). For instance, in Part II, Task 1, analyses of the activities display the presence of remembering and understanding as LOTS indicated by their respective subskills. Sub-skills are listing for remembering and grouping or classifying for understanding. An application of OTS as reinforcement is detected when task 3 is analyzed, they showed evaluating, analyzing and understanding with subskills deciding, choosing and eliminating and reasoning, respectively. As the activities moved to the output, the OTS are interconnected in the approach. To illustrate, Task 10 has a combination of LOTS and HOTS with their corresponding subskills. The table below elucidates the spread and increase of the OTS. Comparably, backed by the median (4), it is believed that through the task designed for students' involvement, the OTS in the CW are highly evident among the respondents. 59.25% among the respondents argue that the OTS' roles to strengthen CW are highly observable in the series of activities. *Table 13* shows some tasks with embedded OTS. Information regarding the functionality of this component is stipulated in *Table 17*.

Median (Mdn)	4
Mode	4
Point value	4
Range	3.41-4.20
Descriptive Rating	high
Percentage	59.25
No of respondents out of 27	16

Table 11: Component C: Order thinking skills application for reinforcement

Task 1 Part 2	Task 3 part 2	Task 10 part 2
some processes along the output	Output -making process	
LOTS	HOTS & LOTS	LOTS & HOTS
OTS & Sub-skills: Remembering -listing Understanding- grouping or classifying	OTS & Sub-skills Evaluating - deciding Analyzing: choosing / eliminating / Understanding: reasoning	OTS & Subskills: Remembering : Transferring Understanding: responding Creating: Writing Analyzing: organizing Evaluating: critiquing, reviewing & checking Applying: Using

Table 12: Examples Order thinking skills integrated in the tasks

To further back this component, *Table 12* shows the summarized OTS manifested by the tasks from LOTS to HOTS that scaffold the CW engagement.

Lower order thinking skills (LOTS)		Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS)				
Remembering	Understanding	Applying	Analyzing	Evaluating	Creating	
Part 1 (p1) & Part 2 tasks (t)						
S U B - S K I L L S	listing (t1) completing/ ordering / sequencing (t2) identifying/ ordering (t5) matching (t6) transferring (t10)	predicting (p1) concluding (p1) abstracting (p1) responding (p1) interpreting (p1) responding (p1) explaining (p1) grouping (t1) transforming(t4) classify (t7) providing/ completing/ concluding (t8) inferring/ concluding/ illustrating/ exemplifying (t9) responding (t10)	using (t4) modifying (t5) using (t5) using (t8) using (t10)	eliminating/ discriminating/ Choosing (t3) eliminating (t3) removing (t6) select (t6) organizing (t10)	choosing/ eliminating/ deciding (t3) critiquing/ reviewing/ checking (t10)	constructing/ creating (t9) generating (t10)

Table 13: Summarized order thinking skills from the tasks

To exemplify *Table13*, the obvious presence of OTS can be corroborated by the subskills embedded among part 1 tasks (p1) and part 2 tasks (t) comprising 10 tasks that demonstrate the strong presence of OTS. In part 1 tasks, there are seven (7) subskills that demonstrate understanding in preparation for their involvement in the part 2 tasks. They include predicting, concluding, abstracting, responding, interpreting, responding and explaining. Moreover, in Tasks 2, it has been emphasized that there are five (5) remembering subskills found in Tasks 1, 2, 5, & 10; eleven (11) for understanding: Task 1, 4, 7, 8, 9 & 10; five (5) for applying: Task 4, 5 ,8 & 10; seven (7) for analyzing: Tasks 3, 6 & 10; six (6) for evaluating: Tasks 3 &10 and three (3) for creating: Task 9 &10.

It can be argued that as the OTS are increased, the lesser, but in depth they are to be dealt with by learners. It can be assumed that as the activities are underpinned by varied OTS, the foundation that directs the participants to the output solidifies the knowledge of direction as a whole, a sign of being equipped with the skill to accomplish the targeted output (Klimovienė, Urbonienė & Barzdžiukienė, 2006; Kurfiss, 2001; Allamnakhrah, 2012; Lambright, 1995; Jaganathan; Orunsolu, Vincent, Adebayo & Bamgboye, 2010; Caviedes, Meza & Rodrigues, 2016; Latawiec, Anderson, Ma & Nguyen 2016).

Component D: Significance of the process to the writing output

In terms of evaluating the writing output on its importance to the teaching procedure, it results to the same mode (4) which further explains that the application of process in

reinforcing CW through the OTS should have an anticipated written output by the teacher. In here, the writing output is dependent on the process involved before it can be truly accomplished. Supportive of the mode (4), the median (4) indicates high association of the process in directing learners for the writing output. This designates the significance of crystal clear procedures to be determined before a successful writing output can be completed by learners. The procedures demonstrated can achieve the CW target of this method (Kauchak & Eggen, 1998; Shirkhani & Fahim, 2011; Shehadeh, 2011; Latawiec, Anderson, Ma & Nguyen, 2016; Huett & Koch, 2011). As seen in *Table 14*, 59% of the respondents' population maintains a high significance of the writing output's necessity to procedures.

Median (Mdn)	4
Mode	4
Point value	4
Range	3.41-4.20
Descriptive Rating	High
Percentage	59.25%
No of respondents out of 27	16

Table 14: Component D: Writing output's significant connection to the process

Component E: Relevance of the KLO framework to the process

The KLO framework is declared to be high indicated by its mode, 4. KLO's relevance to the process shows that K which is equal to Knowledge or information gathering should be first processed. The basis of information from this introduced approach is a silent film. With the mode that is generated, it is presumed that knowledge gathering is pertinent to the procedures in reinforcing CW through the OTS. L in the framework is Language; it has been recognized additionally that the language processing is important. Knowledge and language are the pre-requisites to O which is Organization representing the actual processes of writing. With the mode computed, it reveals that KLO framework as a process is highly recognized by participants while they engrossed with the process of arriving at the written output. To corroborate, median tells a high relevance of the KLO in the whole process of administering this collaborative approach. It can be attributed to the fact that the participants have observed the presence of every component: knowledge, language and organization. If we analyze the whole process being introduced, it stretches as the whole awareness of the KLO. First, it is introduced by a film viewing for the knowledge to be gathered. The tasks after the knowledge are gathered and are broken down into part 1 and part 2. In part 1, the tasks are intended to facilitate the knowledge of the learners. Part 2 tasks continue to boost the awareness about the viewed material incorporating languages that are dominantly deployed in writing. In the later part, under organization, a task is well- strengthened by the rudiments of writing the output. All these are perceived by the participants who supposed that it is highly viable component of demonstrating this said approach. *Table 16* features some tasks classified under the three KLO components which further clarify that the KLO as a framework leads to the collaboration of activities that are found in its components: knowledge, language and organization (Hanjani, 2015; Laal & Ghodsi, 2011; Elola, 2010; Suwantarathip & Wichadee, 2014; Heidar, 2016; Haring-Smith, 1994; Guerrero, Mejias,

Collazos, Pino & Ochoa, 2003). Additionally, 62 % of the respondents adhered to the high viability of KLO in the conduct of CW through OTS reinforcement. *Table 15* features how this is regarded as high in viability through mode (4) and media (4) as well as the percentage (62.59%).

Median (Mdn)	4
Mode	4
Point value	4
Range	3.41-4.20
Descriptive Rating	High
Percentage	62.59 %
No of respondents out of 27	18

Table 15: Component E: Relevance of the KLO framework to the process

Knowledge framework	Language framework	Organization framework
<p>Part 1</p> <p>Task 1 <i>Knowledge Indicators:</i></p> <p>film viewing in establishing idea about the character,</p> <p>making inferences,</p> <p>interpreting the meanings of the symbol,</p> <p>obtaining a background about the short film</p>	<p>Part 2</p> <p>Task 1 <i>Language Indicators:</i></p> <p>listing, grouping or classifying words which under actions, descriptions, people, places and things</p> <p>Task 2 <i>Language Indicators:</i></p> <p>completing, ordering/sequencing through phrases and sentences</p> <p>Task 3 <i>Language Indicators:</i></p> <p>deciding, choosing, eliminating words, phrases</p> <p>Task 4 <i>Language Indicators:</i></p> <p>transforming and using words</p>	<p>Part 2</p> <p>Task 10 <i>Organization Indicators:</i></p> <p>Use the title from the group poster. Title should appear above paragraph 1. State the author, nationality and date of the story's release.</p> <p>Paragraph 2 relates the events from the beginning to the end alongside character's description with time and place of events.</p> <p>Paragraph 3 should contain the message, which the story wants to tell the viewers. Your written activity should bear 3 paragraphs and should connect to the posters made.</p>

Table 16: Examples of tasks classified according to KLO components

In summary, it is supposed that these components in CW which are (1) designed tasks, (2) collaboration process, (3) order thinking skills integration, (4) writing outputs significance to the process and (5) Knowledge- Language and Organization (KLO) congruently contribute to the high viability of the whole procedure statistically proven by the mode (4) and median (4). It is assumed that in order to reinforce CW through the order thinking skills, it is relevant that a well-designed connected activities, complete OTS fused in the activities, specific collaborative procedures gearing to the target exposition and the presence of information gathering, language focus and writing rudiments should be the priorities of instruction. Consistently significant, the KLO plays a main role of being the umbrella of the components.

Table 17 below shows an extensive noteworthy coverage of the framework that facilitates favorable reflection of the teacher in the conduct of this recommended approach.

KLO Framework

<p>Knowledge is generated by the material (film) alongside tasks and OTS.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Was there an appropriate source for information gathering? 2. Did the teacher process the information gathering through varied activities? 3. Did the activities generate interchanges among the participants? 4. Did the activities suffice the information processing? 5. Were there OTS manipulated in this level? 6. Did the activities relate to the CW project? <p>Language/s is/are embedded in the tasks alongside OTS.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Did the teacher provide language foci to be mainly manipulated? 2. Did the teacher stimulate inferences regarding the language activities? 3. Were the forms of language essential in the CW process? 4. Were OTSs manipulated in this level? 5. Did the activities relate to the CW project? <p>Organization involves the tasks for writing, collaboration, alongside language and OTS.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Were there varied activities for the CW project? 2. Was there enough students' time to establish thoughts prior to writing? 3. Were there enough activities for the students to gather knowledge and carry-out the CW process? 4. Were there ways of organizing knowledge of the language and ideas prior to writing? 5. Were OTS manipulated in this level? 6. Did the activities relate to the CW project?

Table 17: KLO Frameworks

5. Findings and pedagogical implications

Researches that underpin the OTS activation as observed	Observed OTS activation from the approach
Kauchak & Eggen, 1998; Shirkhani & Fahim, 2011; Shehadeh, 2011; Latawiec, Anderson, Ma & Nguyen, 2016; Huett & Koch, 2011	After the learners have accomplished the tasks, they thought on how they did the procedures that they have undergone which could aid in refining their common output.
Zaky, 2018; Brookhart, 2010; Grief, 2007; Thomas & Thorne, 2009	Learners recalled what they have gone through in underpinning what they have performed.
Entezari & Taki, 2018; Vijayaratnam, 2012; Ede & Lunsford, 1990; Zhang, 2018; Elola, 2010; Webb, 1982; Kellogg, 2008; Orunsolu, Vincent, Adebayo & Bamgboye, 2010; Caviedes, Meza & Rodrigues, 2016; Talib, & Cheung, 2017; Bakhshayesha, 2016; Aminloo, 2013	HOTS can be stimulated and be enhanced depending on the teaching techniques employed by the teacher in a classroom.
	They were able to identify LOTS from HOTS through the reinforcement of collaborative writing that integrated OTS.
	There were discussions taking place which is a sign that the activities involved HOTS.
	Learning HOTS enhances an individual's mind; leading to the production & sharing of a variety of alternatives, ideas, actions, solutions and designs which are assimilated within a group.

Brindley, Walti & Blaschke, 2009; Benko, 2013; Zaky, 2018; Kauchak & Eggen, 1998; Thomas & Thorne, 2009; Yen & Halili, 2015; Faraj, 2015; Slavin, 1995; Talib & Cheung, 2017; Bodrova & Leong, 1998; Elicker, 1995;	Well-designed materials enable OTS.	The activities that originated from the materials propelled learners increasing OTS from LOTS to HOTS. It has a single material that integrated manipulated OTS through varied activities.
Klimovienė, Urbonienė & Barzdžiukienė, 2006; Kurfiss, 2001; Allamnakhrah, 2012; Lambright, 1995; Jaganathan; Orunsolu, Vincent, Adebayo & Bamgboye, 2010; Caviedes, Meza & Rodrigues, 2016; Latawiec, Anderson, Ma & Nguyen 2016	Varied idea generation is important for the completion of individual assignments for a common project.	Each one shared standpoints of which they were weighed and considered according to weak and strong points.
Klimovienė, Urbonienė & Barzdžiukienė, 2006; Kurfiss, 2001; Vygotsky, 1978; Collins, 2014; Davidson & Major, 2014; Pastor and David Perry, 2010	OTS can be generated through real-life contexts.	Contexts of the writing revolved around societal problems in a film that maneuvered the series of activities aided by their prior thoughts.
Hanjani, 2015; Laal & Ghodsi, 2011; Elola, 2010; Suwantarathip & Wichadee, 2014; Heidar, 2016; Haring-Smith, 1994; Guerrero, Mejias, Collazos, Pino & Ochoa, 2003	OTS can be achieved through collaborative activities.	The series of activities presented were designed for collaboration which was observed in their interactions.
Brindley, Walti & Blaschke, 2009; Benko, 2013; Zaky, 2018; Kauchak & Eggen, 1998; Thomas & Thorne, 2009; Yen & Halili, 2015; Faraj, 2015; Slavin, 1995; Talib & Cheung, 2017; Bodrova & Leong, 1998; Elicker, 1995	HOTS can grow to complete and more complex types of thinking when well-scaffold and facilitated.	They started from LOTS-related activities as they integrate LOTS and HOTS in the construction of the output
Shehadeh, 2011; Latawiec, Anderson, Ma & Nguyen 2016; Brookhart, 2010; Correia, 2006 Kauchak & Eggins, 1998; Brewster, 1999	HOTS commence from fundamental forms of thinking (LOTS) as they branch out to generate other methods of thinking when regularly-supported.	The material (input) and the tasks scaffold groups' performances.
Zaky, 2018; Kauchak & Eggen, 1998; Brindley, Walti & Blaschke, 2009; Thomas & Thorne, 2009;; Faraj, 2015; Shirkhani & Fahim, 2011; ;Vdovina & Gaibisso, 2013; Klimovienė, Urbonienė & Barzdžiukienė, 2006; Singh, Singh, Tunku, Mostafa & Singh, 2018; Rao, 2007	HOTS could be created through well-directed second language activities that are manifested by process and variety of activities	The activities were their guide in the performance of the output; questions raised by the groups involved OTS at any level.
Churches, 2008; Lidawan & Chua, 2018; Lidawan & Gabayno, 2018; Lambright, 1995; Allamnakhrah, 2012	When OTS are continuously taught and applied, they can be transformed into contemporary ways of learning such as digital taxonomy for digital literacy that situate current learners' needs.	The digital material from the YouTube tended to serve as an eye-opener to digital taxonomy due to the basics of technology initially presented. Googling, surfing among other engagement, may introduce digital participations.

Table 18: Findings on the potentials of order thinking skills (OTS) during the presentation of tasks

6.1 Observed implications of this approach

Some relevant points are recognized during the demonstration of this approach. OTS tend to be more augmented through introducing variety of activities (Zaky, 2018; Kauchak & Eggen, 1998; Brindley, Walti & Blaschke, 2009; Thomas & Thorne, 2009; Faraj, 2015; Shirkhani & Fahim, 2011; Vdovina & Gaibisso, 2013; Klimovienė, Urbonienė & Barzdžiukienė, 2006; Singh, Singh, Tunku, Mostafa & Singh, 2018; Rao, 2007). OTS can be more presented through the utilization of springboards fascinating to the learners; knowledge that occurs within their previous environmental exposures can add to their motivation (Klimovienė, Urbonienė & Barzdžiukienė, 2006; Kurfiss, 2001; Vygotsky, 1978; Collins, 2014; Davidson & Major, 2014; Pastor and David Perry, 2010). OTS can be stirred through more facilitation of activities that involve learners in vocabulary, grammar and macro skills such as writing collaboratively. OTS can be enriched through the creation of integrated skills approach alongside well-designed tasks created from (a) potentially engrossing material/s to be performed with students' collaboration (Brindley, Walti & Blaschke, 2009; Benko, 2013; Zaky, 2018; Kauchak & Eggen, 1998; Thomas & Thorne, 2009; Yen & Halili, 2015; Faraj, 2015; Slavin, 1995; Talib & Cheung, 2017; Bodrova & Leong, 1998; Elicker, 1995). OTS can be upgraded through the exploration of task-based teaching engaging the KLO framework aside from writing; collaborative listening and reading can be explored through this groundwork. OTS possibly expands by creatively adapting activities to supplement textbook-given undertakings; constant integration of innovative activities that may direct students' motivation to participate is supportive. OTS can be activated when objectives are based from the intended output/s as (a) performance indicator/s; the subskills are proposed to be the foci of the objectives in proximity to the intended outputs; provides appropriate directions to teachers and students in instructive processes. Also, this teaching style tends to activate the use of teaching methods/principles such as scaffolding, (Brindley, Walti & Blaschke, 2009; Benko, 2013; Zaky, 2018; Kauchak & Eggen, 1998; Thomas & Thorne, 2009; Yen & Halili, 2015; Faraj, 2015; Slavin, 1995; Talib & Cheung, 2017; Bodrova & Leong, 1998; Elicker, 1995), task-based, content-based, communicative language teaching, integrated skills, Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL), digital taxonomy (Zaky, 2018; Brookhart, 2010; Grief, 2007; Thomas & Thorne, 2009) and principles of materials designs.

7. Application of reinforcing collaborative writing approach by order thinking skills

7.1 Material

The material utilized to construct creative tasks for CW is downloaded from YouTube's short silent film entitled, *Wings* (Raveendran, 2013).

7.2 Collaborative writing tasks

The tasks are composed of Part 1 and Part 2. Part 1 comprises while-viewing and after-viewing activities with the purpose of providing learners' knowledge to actively participate in Part 2 tasks. Thus, Part 1 is analyzed as activities belonging to the knowledge component of the KLO framework containing understanding as its LOTS stipulated by the stimulated subskills. Many Researchers such as (Benko, 2013; Kauchak & Eggen, 1998; Correia, 2006;

Brewster, 1999; Vdovina & Gaibisso, 2013; Jaganathan & Subramaniam, 2016; Bikowski, & Vithanage, 2016; Grief, 2007; Shirkhani & Fahim, 2011; Wilks, 2005; Vygotsky, 1962; Brookhart, 2010; Handley & Miner, 1998; Lidawan & Chua, 2007; Lidawan & Gabayno; Thomas & Thorne, 2009; Yen & Halili, 2015; Kurfiss, 2001) advocate, in one way or another, the essentials of a well-planned, designed and facilitated tasks that dominantly interplay with OTS.

Part I: While-viewing questions

Answer the following questions:

- 1) What do you think will the character do at the end of the story? Use a short sentence to answer.
- 2) What message does the movie want to bring to its audience? Use a short sentence to answer.

After-viewing question

- 3) What does “wings” mean in the movie? Use a short sentence to answer the question.

Part 1: Task Breakdown

Understanding: (LOTS) Sub-skills: predicting, abstracting, interpreting, responding & explaining; KLO Framework Component: knowledge

Part 2 is composed of post-viewing tasks. It contains 10 collaborative tasks that are similarly analyzed according to OTS as indicated by the subskills and the KLO framework each task belongs gearing towards the accomplishment of the targeted writing output.

Part II: Post-viewing tasks

Task 1

List as many actions, descriptions, people, places and things found in the movie. Group/classify them by using the table.

actions descriptions people, places and things

actions	descriptions	people, places and things
_____	_____	_____
_____	_____	_____
_____	_____	_____

Task 1 Breakdown

Remembering: (LOTS) Sub-skills: listing; Understanding: (LOTS): grouping or classifying
Framework Component: Language

Task 2

Complete the diagram by writing the events that took place in the story and order them according to how they happened. Use numbers 1 to 8. 1 is done for you.

Task 2 Breakdown

Remember: (LOTS): Subskills: completing, ordering/sequencing; Framework Component: Language

Task 3

Choose the groups of words that connect to the story by ticking (✓). Eliminate the group of words that do not connect to the story by crossing out (X): early morning, quiet urban area, young man woke up, cooing pigeon, drove it away, picked a piece of concrete, flew away, rainbow appeared, strange idea happened, trembling hand, spread his arms like flapping wings, crippled bird, gesturing similar motion, happened in winter, a winged–animal appeared, screaming loud, hopping towards the edge of the skyscraper's roof, gaped at the rising sun, shaking his head, people warning him, took a fatal leap, said goodbye to his parents, walking along the road.

Task 3 Breakdown

Understanding: (LOTS) Subskills: reasoning; Analyzing: (HOTS) Subskills: choosing/eliminating; Evaluating: (HOTS) Subskills: deciding; Framework Component: Language

Task 4

Present simple (singular)	Past simple	Past continuous (singular)
wakes up	woke up	was waking up
spends		
	caught	
tries		
	remained	
	picked	
		was flinging
	flew	

		was watching
		was occurring
stares		
	fixed	
	turned	
	gestured	

Transform the given verbs into present simple, past simple and past continuous simple. Use the rules of changing regular and irregular verbs. Some were done for you.

Task 4 Breakdown

Understanding: (LOTS) Sub-skill: transforming; Applying: (HOTS) Sub-skill: using; Framework Component: Language

Task 5

Identify the present simple verbs in the boxes. Modify these verbs by changing them into past simple verbs. Place the events in correct order by writing letters A, B, C, D, E, F and G.

<i>He slowly stands and hops like a bird moving closer towards the edge.</i>	<i>He sees a pigeon and tries to drive it away. He picks a piece of concrete and flings it to the bird.</i>
<i>He stares at his trembling right hand as it slowly fixes the movement of a flapping wing.</i>	<i>The man takes a fatal leap.</i>
<i>He gazes down at city's street then gapes at the rising sun.</i>	<i>A young man wakes up and finds himself on a high building's roof.</i>
<i>He turned to his left hand that is slowly gesturing similar motion.</i>	

Task 5 Breakdown

Remembering: (LOTS) Sub-skills: Identifying & ordering; Applying: (HOTS) Sub-skills: modifying & using; Framework Component: Language & knowledge

Task 6

Match the pairs of the following words. Tick (✓) if they have the same meanings and Cross out (x) if they are of opposite meanings. No. 4 is an example.

Words	Answers	Meanings
quiet	A.	noisy place
urban	B.	far from the city
pigeon	C.	a kind of butterfly
remained	X	move out
concrete	E.	a solid material
flung	F.	threw it towards
swiftly	G.	slowly move

steadily		H.	doesn't move right away
hovering		I.	flying away
a weird		J.	something common
occurred		K.	thought of something
trembling		L.	shaking
flapping		M.	spreading wings
hopped		N.	leaping
edge		O.	limit of something/brink
skyscraper		P.	a tower/ high building
gaped		Q.	looked
leap		R.	jump

Task 6 Breakdown

Remembering: (LOTS) Sub-skill: matching; Analyzing: (HOTS) Sub-skills: eliminating/ removing/ discriminating; Framework Component: Language

Task 7

A. Select expressions for sequencing events from the table by encircling them.

at first	also
because	next,
then	will
later	during this time
one main reason	finally
contrary	for instance
or	in the end
after that	however
before	for the reason that
since	for example
unless	and
but	in comparison
when	similarly

B. Classify the words from the table by writing them in the below boxes.

Box 1

Box 2

Expressions
in sequencing events

Other expressions that are not used
in sequencing events

Task 7 Breakdown

Analyzing: (HOTS) Sub-skill: Selecting; Understanding: (LOTS) Sub-skill: classifying
Framework Component: Language

Task 8

Provide continuations of the incomplete sentences using factual information from the story.

1. When he woke up, _____.

2. He picked a piece of concrete and _____.
3. While the dove was flying, _____.
4. Both of his hands _____ like _____.
5. He stood and _____.
6. He continued to _____ till he reached the roof's _____.
7. He looked down then stared up at the _____.
8. Finally, the young man _____.

Task 8 Breakdown

Understanding: (LOTS) Sub-skills: providing/completing or concluding; Applying: (HOTS) Sub-skill: using; Framework Component: Language

Task 9

Construct a poster of your story by drawing symbols that give the message of the film to all viewers. Create your own title.

Task 9 Breakdown

Creating: (HOTS) Sub-skills: constructing and creating; Understanding: (LOTS) Sub-skills: inferring, concluding, illustrating or exemplifying; Framework Component: Language and organization

Task 10

Organize information from the story by answering the questions in complete statements.

1. Title: What's the title of your story?

2. Author, nationality and date of released: Who is the author of the story? What is the author's nationality? When was the film made?

3. Character/s: Name the main character in the story. Describe the character. (What is he like?)

4. Setting: Where and when did it happen?

5. Events: State the events in the story by combining past simple and past continuous simple. Connect the events by using sequencing expressions.

6. Theme/Message: What theme/message does the story want to tell its viewers? Use present simple tense to answer.

7. Use the organization reminders* below to guide your writing activity.

Organization Reminders*:

1. Your title should appear before your paragraphs. Use the title from the group's poster made in task 9.
2. The first paragraph should state the author, nationality and date of the story's release.
3. The second paragraph should relate the events from the beginning to the end including the character's description (s) /time and place of events.
4. The third paragraph should contain the message which the story wants to tell the viewers.
5. You should write 3 paragraphs.
6. Refer to the activities to answer the questions.
7. Review information by watching the film for the second time.

Task 10 Breakdown

Remembering: LOTS- Sub-skill; Transferring & Stating; Understanding: LOTS –Sub-skill: responding; Creating: HOTS –Sub-skill: Writing; Analyzing: HOTS- Sub- skill: organizing; Evaluating: HOTS-Sub-skill: critiquing, reviewing & checking; Applying: HOTS- sub-skill: Using; Framework Component: Organization

8. Recommendations

The paper's recommendations for general and specific purposes are anchored to students' development, teachers' professional development, institutional responsibility and further researches.

8.1 Students' Development

While this writing approach spawned a viable result applicable to teaching as considered by language educators, it is best to test the viability of this writing methodology through students' OTS tasks performance which this is primarily conceptualized for.

Foundation writing students need background knowledge prior to writing (Marzano, R. (2004). At this juncture, students' should be immersed to information and the language they have to manipulate scaffold by activities. Besides, even the writing process itself should contain scaffolding exercises (Slavin, 1995; Kauchan & Eggen, 1998; Talib & Cheung, 2017; Bodrova & Leong, 1998; Elicker, 1995). Thus, KLO framework is hereby highly recommended.

It is offered that integrating OTS to reinforce CW can take place through guided writing alongside its procedures that confine variety of students' tasks (Kauchak & Eggen, 1998; Shirkhani & Fahim, 2011; Shehadeh, 2011; Latawiec, Anderson, Ma & Nguyen, 2016; Huett & Koch, 2011).

Collaboration principles that define sociocognition (Vygotsky, 1978; Collins, 2014; Davidson & Major, 2014; Fung, 2010; Singh, Singh, Tunku, Mostafa & Singh, 2018; Klimovienė, Urbonienė & Barzdžiukienė, 2006) should be accentuated in all activities that we

offer our students for motivation and interpersonal interaction to generate or condition their styles of learning. Every educator should be aware that positive rate of students' classroom participation can be realized when instructions are teacher-centered. Trending style for instruction in the 21st century should be perceived as more on facilitation (Vygotsky, 1978; Collins, 2014; Bruner, 1986; Lunsford, 1991; Davidson & Major, 2014).

Learners' OTS increased when every activity a teacher presents corresponds to (a) specific objective/s. The aim of the activities produce OTS that may be covered under LOTS or HOTS whether the skills tested are receptive (listening/viewing, reading) or productive (speaking and writing). This additionally delineates the purpose why we need to present learning objectives prior to the conduct of lessons as well as being specific when preparing teaching blueprints. The objectives that we stipulate are the subskills that determine the level of learners' OTSs useful in triggering their CT (Benko, 2013; Kauchak and Eggins, 1998; Correia, 2006; Brewster, 1999; Vdovina & Gaibisso, 2013; Jaganathan & Subramaniam, 2016; Bikowski, & Vithanage, 2016; Grief, 2007; Shirkhani & Fahim, 2011; Wilks, 2005; Vygotsky, 1962; Brookhart, 2010; Handley & Miner, 1998; Lidawan & Chua, 2007; Lidawan & Gabayno; Thomas & Thorne, 2009; Yen & Halili, 2015; Kurfiss, 2001).

8.2 Professional Development

Teachers should be immersed to techniques and instructional designs in conjunction to how OTS are explored in the classroom. There is a need for teachers' exposures regarding these specified elements of 21st century learning: collaboration and CT for students. As contemporary language instructors being defined by learners' environment, level, time and educational transformations; educators should continue to search answers to these changes through workshops, seminars, trainings, peer teacher-involvement among other forms of professional development (self-directed or institutionally instigated) to address and impact the real essence of contemporary classroom instructions (Bourn, 2015; Stronge, Grant & Xu, 2015; Rotherham, & Willingham, 2009; Wei, Darling-Hammond & Adamson, 2010; Fullan, 1991).

8.3 Institutional Responsibility

Every institution's academic program should manifest acceptance of teachers' strategic creativity. The management should not control how language coaches deliver and what the teacher should use in presenting their lessons unless contrary to teaching principles. They should be directed to employ sanctioned ethics that contribute to generally practice standardized instructional process to augment learners' critical thinking in all the skills being instructed; encourage innovative guidelines that stir the presence of students' collaborative participation ((Brindley, Walti & Blaschke, 2009; Wilks, 2005; Brindley, Walti & Blaschke, 2009).

Stipulation of collaboration, problem-solving and critical thinking in the learning areas should be among the writing curricula's priority. These should be indicated by educational organizations' strategic goals (Gokhale, 1995; Talib & Chung, 2017; Singh, Singh, Tunku, Mostafa & Singh, 2018; Klimovienė, Urbonienė & Barzdžiukienė, 2006).

8.4 Further Researches

It is recommended that a specific investigation gearing to this methodology be performed. This may be conducted to greater population of respondents to determine their OTS' attitudes and levels or to teachers' perceptions regarding OTS that could determine their extent of practice or on their OTS' awareness in conjunction to material designs and teaching techniques statistically measuring CW through OTS' effects, strengths and weaknesses to produce reflective standpoints or frameworks which contemporary language trainers can model or utilize as fundamental framework.

9. Conclusion

As signposted by the calculated median and the mode from nominal collected data, *Reinforcing Collaborative Writing through Order Thinking Skills* tends to be viable. It is recognized that with the aid of the five constituents, the proposed approach possibly will be facilitated to learners.

The writer always has had in mind that CW can never be greatly demonstrated in the absence of scaffolding process. This process may perhaps be manifested by created tasks integrating the encouragement of OTS under the umbrella of a background containing the rudiments of knowledge collaboration, language and organization to sustain the commencement and the end of a socially and academically-rewarding writing engagement.

Reinforcement of CW through OTS opens doors to learning the language away from isolation, but should be interactive and contextually engaging. In here, it gears to discover people realizing thoughts through appropriate reasoning that originates from LOT to HOTS and people learning from one another through weighing and considering points of what possibly will be sanctioned or rejected leading towards a common writing purpose. At this point, pondering on the best style to teach students, defines a real educator as Bourn, (2015), Stronge, Grant & Xu (2015), Wei, Darling-Hammond & Adamson (2010), Rotherham, & Willingham (2009) and Fullan (1991) suggest that language mentors should see themselves as mediators rather than objects of transformation. Globally, teachers are viewed upon as individuals who can assist to bring about constructive changes in the lives of 21st century language learners.

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